

CLEWs: A Pathway to Greener Agriculture in Tamil Nadu

- Balaji Lakshmi Narayanan,
Centre for Climate Change and Disaster Management, Anna University, India
- 21st August 2024

Keywords: CLEWs, WEF Nexus, Renewable energy resources, Solar Pump, Surface and Groundwater Irrigation

Acknowledgements

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to Kane Alexander, Francesco Gardumi, Salsabila Abdulhalim, Shravan Kannan, and Leigh Martindale for their invaluable training and unwavering support throughout the CLEWs program. I am also deeply appreciative of the institutions that have supported these trainers, including Imperial College London, the Technical University of Mombasa, and KTH Royal Institute of Technology. Special thanks to Climate Compatible Growth, the International Centre for Theoretical Physics, the World Bank Group, and Sustainable Energy for All for organizing the EMP-G and making this experience possible. I also acknowledge the Centre for Climate Change and Disaster Management at Anna University, for their continuous support. Additionally, my participation in EMP-G was generously funded by Climate Compatible Growth, for which I am deeply grateful.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

This study examines the effects of transitioning to Renewable Energy (RE) and upgrading the irrigation system with solar pumps in Tamil Nadu, India, focusing on the climate, land, energy, and water sectors. Using the CLEWs framework and the OSeMOSYS tool, three scenarios were analyzed: Business As Usual (BAU), RE Transition, and RE Transition with Solar Pumps. The study evaluates their impacts on emissions, land use, and water demand.

The results indicate that the RE Transition scenario, which relies on renewable energy, results in the lowest emissions and water usage. Additionally, replacing diesel and electric pumps with solar pumps can significantly cut CO₂ emissions by 20 million tonnes per year and 44.5 billion cubic meters of water are conserved. The study highlights the value of CLEWs NEXUS modelling for ensuring sustainable and renewable energy solutions in irrigation.

Recommendations include integrating water and land management strategies into energy planning, prioritizing investments in renewable energy with minimal water and land impacts, and exploring various technologies to address energy and climate needs while reducing carbon emissions and environmental effects.

1. Introduction

India is the world's most populous country, with its population projected to reach 1.5 billion by 2030 and exceed 1.7 billion by 2050, according to the UN. Tamil Nadu (TN) is the sixth most populous state in India, occupying 3.9% of the nation's total geographical area. The state faces severe water stress, with overexploitation of water resources leading to declining water tables. This scarcity heavily impacts vital sectors such as agriculture, power generation, and industry. Climate change is expected to worsen these challenges, further straining already stressed water resources.

India has pledged to achieve net-zero emissions by 2070 and aims to secure 50% of its cumulative electric power installed capacity from non-fossil fuel sources by 2030, as outlined in the updated Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) submitted in 2022. Tamil Nadu has been a leader in renewable energy (RE) initiatives, with an impressive ~55% of its installed capacity coming from renewable sources as of November 2023.

However, despite this achievement, renewable energy currently contributes only ~21% to the state's total energy output. Tamil Nadu has set a target to increase this share to 50% by 2030. As the eleventh largest producer of food grains in India, Tamil Nadu's electricity consumption for agricultural purposes is 50.38 PJ (Agricultural Statistics, 2022 Govt. of India), largely due to the use of pumps for irrigation. According to the Economics and Statistics Report of Tamil Nadu, the state has 2,181,330 electric pumps and 278,600 diesel

pumps. Based on the Central Groundwater Board Assessment 2023, It is estimated that more than 100 firkas are over exploited in Tamil Nadu State due to excessive pumping. The groundwater category assessment map of Tamil Nadu is shown in the Figure. The basic outline of groundwater status, water demand and landuse is shown in the Figure.1

Figure 1. a.Tamil Nadu Water Demand, **b.**Power Generation Capacity, **c.**Land Use Land Cover and **d.** Groundwater Category Units – Baseline

The central government is working to solarize agricultural pumps under various schemes, including Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha evam Utthaan Mahabhiyan (PM-KUSUM), to decarbonize the agricultural sector. By August 2022, Tamil Nadu had installed 7,701 stand-alone solar pumps under KUSUM (Ministry of New and Renewable Energy 2022).

The primary objective of this study is to assess the impact of the RE transition and the integration of solar pumps on emission scenarios and water demand. Additionally, the study aims to evaluate the effects of different scenarios on emissions, land and water use, and to offer insights and recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders. By analyzing these scenarios in the context of Tamil Nadu, this study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discussions on sustainable energy transitions and climate mitigation strategies.

2. Methodology

In this research, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) framework was applied using the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool. While OSeMOSYS was originally developed for energy systems analysis, its functionality and flexibility permit its adaptation to the integrated analysis of CLEWs. This approach facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, enabling a whole systems approach to decision-making (Howells et al., 2013; Ramos et al., 2019). The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit for India served as the baseline model. Additionally, agriculture, water and energy data were sourced from Department of Economics and Statistics of Tamil Nadu, Tamil Nadu Water Resources, Tamil Nadu Generation and Distribution Corporation, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), National Remote Sensing Centre (NRSC), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

Three scenarios were developed: Business As Usual (BAU), RE Transition, and RE Transition with Solar Pumps. The Business As Usual scenario represents the current state with no policy or resource constraints. The RE Transition scenario introduces RE Min Target : 70 % by 2070; RE Tag Technology: Solar (SOL), Wind (WND), Hydro (HYD) aligned with India's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). The RE Transition with Solar Pumps Scenario aims for a revamping of electric pump into solar pump in the agriculture sector by 2070, with Agriculture Energy Demand Constraints : 100% Solar by 2070. The Key assumptions and summary of the scenarios is given in the Figure.2.

Figure 2.Summary of Scenarios and its Key Assumption

3. Results

This modelling exercise explored the following research question:

What impact does adopting Renewable Energy Transition with solar-based pumping systems have on the CO₂ emissions of Tamil Nadu?

Results revealed distinct trajectories across the three scenarios: Business As Usual (BAU), RE Transition, and RE Transition with Solar Pumps, each shedding light on critical facets of the transition. The Power generation capacity of the three scenarios is shown in the Figure 3:

- In the Business As Usual scenario, Coal emerges as a primary player in power production, necessitating the lowest capital investment yet yielding the highest emissions rates
- The RE Transition scenario witnesses a considerable integration of Hydro and Solar in the energy mix, accompanied by a 100.4% surge in capital investment and considerable reduction up to 1035.2 Mt of CO₂ emission by 2070
- The RE Transition with Solar Pumps, increases the solar pump generation capacity by 96GW and reduces CO₂ emission by 19.2 Mt in the agriculture sector

The examination of CO₂-equivalent emissions across the three scenarios shows distinct trajectories and implications for climate mitigation within the power sector.

In the Business As Usual scenario, total emissions remain notably high throughout the analysis period. This elevated emission level is primarily attributed to the substantial use of fossil fuels, particularly coal, gas, and coal, for power generation. The business-as-usual

scenario, highlighting the relevance of alternative strategies to curb emissions and align with global climate goals.

Figure 3.Total Power Generation Capacity by Scenario

The RE Transition scenario presents a shift towards renewable energy sources like hydro, solar and biofuel power generation, aiming to align emissions with climate targets. While this transition contributes to a significant decrease in emissions compared to the Business As Usual scenario, emissions remain notably higher than those projected in the RE Transition scenario. This exemplifies the complexity of balancing emissions reduction objectives with the need to maintain energy security and affordability.

In the RE Transition with Solar Pumps scenario, characterised by a progressive transition towards solar pump utilisation for agricultural pumping, total emissions exhibit a substantial decrease in the agriculture sector. This scenario achieves the lowest emissions rate among the three scenarios, aligning closely with India’s climate objectives and demonstrating the potential of renewable energy to drive significant emissions reductions within the power sector. The total emission of three scenarios is given in the Figure.4.

Figure 4.Total Emissions by Scenario

The revamping of irrigation system in the Tamil Nadu state through installation of solar based pumping systems, considerably reduces the emission by 20 million tonnes per year in Agriculture Sector is shown in the Figure.5. On comparison with the RE transition scenario, the complete shifting of agricultural pumps further reduces the CO2 emissions . It is estimated that decrease in CO2 emission by 96% at the end of the Scenario in Agriculture Sector.

Figure 5.Total Emissions in Agriculture Sector by Scenario

Based on the scenario analysis, 44.5 billion cubic meters of water are conserved in the RE_Transition scenario with solar pumps on comparison with the BAU Scenario (Figure.6). The total capital investment required to achieve the RE transition with solar pumps is 973.2 billion USD, which is 102% increase in the capital cost on comparison with the BAU scenario. The capital cost for different scenarios is shown in the Figure.7

Figure 6.Total Water Demand in Agriculture Sector by Scenario

Figure 7.Total Emissions in Agriculture Sector by Scenario

4. Discussion

This study made an initial assessment for developing climate-resilient irrigation practices in water-deficit regions

Current irrigation practices often rely solely on surface water or groundwater. When the monsoon fails in a year, groundwater dependency is excessive, leading to groundwater level depletion. This nexus approach adopted in this study optimised the surface and groundwater conjunctively to maximise water use efficiency and minimise groundwater stress. It is identified from this study, 44.5BCM amount of water conserved on comparison with the BAU Scenario. At the same time, the revamping of solar based pumping system reduce the energy footprint considerably by 96% in agriculture sector.

It is imperative to explore the existing nexus between water resources for irrigation systems by surface or groundwater resources. Additionally, the farmers’ net economic return is essential to be explored from the perspective of energy and water consumption. The rate of groundwater pumping is directly correlated with electricity consumption. Keeping the groundwater pumping rate within the optimal range will be crucial in the coming decades to maintain sustainable water table levels.

The policymakers may consider the Agrivoltaics, the practice of combining agriculture with solar photovoltaic (PV) energy production on the same land, offers several benefits across the Water-Energy-Food (WEF) Nexus. This innovative approach helps address the interlinked challenges of water scarcity, energy demand, and food security.

The limitations of the study, it is assumed that proportion of the crop growing area is uniform for the considered crops, also the crop water requirement of specified crop and hydrological balance of the land components and crop is calculated in the lumped manner. It is better to account the crop water requirement and utilisation of the groundwater from the aquifer should be considered. Considering these constraints leads to opportunities of future

research that builds upon this foundation, expanding the model to provide a more faithful representation of Tamil Nadu complex energy, land and water systems.

Potential areas for future research will consider utilisation of hydrological models to account the water balance components in the CLEWs framework also to consider the possible climate change scenario assessment as per Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) Scenarios. With the potential climate stress, RE target, there is a possible space to explore the crop productivity with the minimal water requirement for sustainable Water Energy Food Nexus through CLEWs.

5. Conclusion

This study has explored the interplay between Renewable Energy technology transitions and energy, land and water systems in Tamil Nadu. By analysing three scenarios - Business As Usual (BAU), RE Transition, and RE Transition with Solar Pumps - this research has gleaned insights into the potential implications of adopting an integrated systems approach. Findings underscore the importance of efficient irrigation system with RE technology as critical components in assessing the emission and cost perspective of power technology transitions. Moving forward, it is recommended that policymakers and stakeholders in the energy sector to prioritise investments in renewable energy sources with lower environmental footprints while exploring innovative solutions to mitigate the impact of greenhouse gas emissions. By embracing a systemic approach that integrates energy, land and water considerations, Tamil Nadu can pave the way for a more sustainable and resilient climate future.

References

- Central Ground Water Authority, 2023. National Compilation on Dynamic Ground Water Resources of India 2023 Available at: <<https://cgwa-noc.gov.in/LandingPage/LatestUpdate/NCDGWR2023.pdf>> [Accessed 21 August 2024].
- FAO, 2024. *AQUASTAT Dissemination System*. [online] Available at: <https://data.apps.fao.org/aquastat/?lang=en> [Accessed 21 August 2024].
- Government of Tamil Nadu, 2021. Statistical Hand Book of Tamil Nadu 2020-21 Available at: <https://www.tn.gov.in/deptst/agriculture.pdf> [Accessed 21 August 2024].
- Howells, M., Hermann, S., Welsch, M., Bazilian, M., Segerström, R., Alfstad, T., Gielen, D., Rogner, H., Fischer, G., Van Velthuis, H. and Wiberg, D., 2013. Integrated analysis of climate change, land-use, energy and water strategies. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(7), pp.621-626.
- Martindale, L., Alexander, K., Gardumi, F., Shivakumar, A. (July, 2023) My First CLEWs Country Model. *Zenodo*. 10.5281/zenodo.7916224
- Ramos, E.P., Sridharan, V., Alfstad, T., Niet, T., Shivakumar, A., Howells, M.I., Rogner, H. and Gardumi, F., 2022. Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems interactions—From key concepts to model implementation with OSeMOSYS. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 136, pp.696-716.
- Ramos, E.P., Howells, M., Sridharan, V., Engström, R.E., Taliotis, C., Mentis, D., Gardumi, F., de Strasser, L., Pappis, I., Balderrama, G.P. and Almulla, Y., 2021. The climate, land, energy, and water systems (CLEWs) framework: a retrospective of activities and advances to 2019. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(3), p.033003.
- TNGCC and CEEW. 2024. Tamil Nadu's Greenhouse Gas Inventory and Pathways for Net-Zero Transition. Chennai: Tamil Nadu Green Climate Company, Department of Environment, Climate Change and Forest, Government of Tamil Nadu; and Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW).

